

Purification of SLC7A1 from Expi293F™ Cells

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Protocol description

This protocol is used to purify the SLC transporter expressed in Expi293F™ Cells using detergent solubilization followed by a series of different chromatographic methods. Depending on the nature of the expression construct and experimental requirements, the GFP tag can be removed using a proteolytic reaction.

Materials

Biological materials:	
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ HEPES (Apollo Scientific, catalog number BI8181)▪ NaCl (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number S9888)▪ LMNG (Lauryl Maltose Neopentyl Glycol) (Anatrace, catalog number NG310)▪ Cholesteryl Hemisuccinate Tris Salt (CHS) (Anatrace, catalog number CH210)▪ cOmplete™, EDTA-free Protease Inhibitor Cocktail (Roche, catalog number 11873580001)▪ Imidazole (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number 56750)▪ Magnesium Chloride Hexahydrate (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number M2670)▪ Glycerol (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number G5516)▪ Adenosine 5-triphosphate disodium salt hydrate, Sigma Aldrich catalog number A2383)▪ TALON® Metal Affinity Resin, (Takara Bio, catalog number 635653)▪ Strep-Tactin®XT 4Flow® high capacity resin (IBA Life Sciences, catalog number 2-5030-025)▪ D(+)-Biotin (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number 851209)▪ TEV (Tobacco Etch Virus) protease (produced in-house)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ WHEATON® Dounce Tissue Grinder, 40 mL (DWK Life Sciences, catalog number 357546)▪ Gravity flow columns▪ 50 kDa cut-off centrifugal concentrators▪ 96 well block (2 mL)

Reagents setup

- **Stock Solution:** 100 mM ATP –NaOH pH 7.5
- **Stock Solution:** 5% (w/v) LMNG/CHS in the ratio of 10:1, prepared in Base buffer. Rotate at 4 °C overnight to allow complete solubilisation and store at -20 °C.
- **Stock Solution:** 250 mM D-biotin in Base buffer. Adjust the pH with NaOH to 7.5 and store at -20 °C.
- Base buffer (50 mM HEPES-NaOH pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 5% Glycerol)
- TALON wash buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 10 mM Imidazole, 10 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM ATP, 5% Glycerol, 0.003% LMNG/CHS)
- TALON elution buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 300 mM Imidazole, 5% Glycerol, 0.003% LMNG/CHS)
- Strep wash buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 1 mM ATP-NaOH, 10 mM MgCl₂, 5% Glycerol, 0.003% LMNG/CHS)
- Strep elution buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 50 mM Biotin, 5% Glycerol, 0.003% LMNG/CHS)

- SEC buffer (20 mM HEPES-NaOH pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 0.002% LMNG/CHS), filtered through 0.22 µM membrane

Procedure

▪ Part A of protocol / day 1

1. Thaw the frozen cell pellet in a water bath set to room temperature.
2. Add 3 tablets of Protease Inhibitor Cocktail tablet to 150 mL of base buffer containing 1% LMNG/CHS. Allow the tablets to dissolve.
3. Suspend thawed pellets with solubilization buffer and pour into a Dounce homogeniser. Homogenise the solution by pulling and pushing the plunger up and down approximately 20 times. Keep on ice.
4. Rotate the container slowly for 1 hour at 4 °C.
5. Centrifuge the solution at 50,000 x g for 30 min at 4 °C.
6. Equilibrate 4-6 mL bed volume of TALON resin with the base buffer.
7. Collect the supernatant and add equilibrated TALON resin to the supernatant, rotate for 1 hour at 4 °C.
8. Transfer the solution to a gravity flow column, allow the solution to flow through.
9. Wash the resin with 10 times the bed volume of TALON wash buffer.
10. Perform elution with 5 times the bed volume of TALON elution buffer.
11. Equilibrate 4-6 mL bed volume of strep XT resin with TALON elution buffer.
12. Add equilibrated strep XT resin to the eluted solution, put on a rotator and rotate for 1 hour at 4 °C.
13. Pour the solution into an empty gravity flow column, allow the solution to flow through.
14. Wash the resin with 10 times the bed volume of strep wash buffer.
15. Perform 3-4 serial elutions with 3-5 mL of strep elution buffer each. Let the column stand for 15-20 minutes between each elution.
16. Measure protein concentration using nanodrop. If the protein has a TEV cleavage site followed by a GFP tag (and if the GFP tag needs removal), add TEV protease to the protein solution in a 1:5 to 1:10 (w/w) TEV:protein ratio.
17. Slowly rotate the container overnight at 4 °C.

▪ Part B of protocol / day 2

18. In a gravity flow column, equilibrate 2-4 mL bed volume of TALON resin with SEC buffer.
19. Add equilibrated TALON resin to the overnight TEV reaction mixture and rotate for 1 hour at 4 °C.
20. Using an empty gravity flow column let the solution collect flow through solution in a 50 kDa cut-off centrifugal filter.
21. Concentrate the solution by centrifuging at 3,000 xg at 4 °C, stop and gently agitate every 5 minutes.
22. Equilibrate a Superdex® 200 Increase 10/300 GL column using SEC buffer.
23. Concentrate the sample down to the desired injection volume and inject the sample into the sample loop.
24. Run a SEC elution.
25. Pool peak fractions in a fresh 50 kDa cut-off centrifugal concentrator and concentrate to the required volume/concentration at 3,000 xg at 4 °C.

Additional notes

1. The amount of solubilisation buffer depends on the cell pellet volume. We recommend using 30-40 mL solubilisation buffer per litre cell culture. The above protocol has been adapted for cell pellet from 4 L culture.
2. The TEV treatment step is to be carried out only if the GFP tag needs to be removed.

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Data availability

References

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.